

Deliverable D3.2 Toolkit extension based on first wave demonstrators

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¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/intranet/data-management-network/members>

Log of changes

DATE	Mvm	Who	Description
05/07/2021	0v1	Inge Jonassen (UiB) Korbinian Bösl (UiB)	Initial version
16/07/2021	0v2	Inge Jonassen (UiB) Korbinian Bösl (UiB)	Sent to PMU after incorporating internal WP feedback
19/7/2021	0v3	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Circulated to the MB for final review before submission
26/7/2021	0v4	Inge Jonassen (UiB) Korbinian Bösl (UiB)	MB comments addressed
27/7/2021	1v0	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version to be uploaded into EC Portal

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1. Executive Summary

The scope of deliverable D3.2 is the extension of the content of the WP3 data management toolkit (named RDMkit) based on the first wave of demonstrator projects (WP5). In order to achieve the deliverable, we established and applied processes to allow communities to contribute and extend the content of the RDMkit, including the ones involved in the first wave of demonstrator projects.

As already reported in D3.1: “The ELIXIR RDMkit is intended to support researchers and data ×stewards to enable lifecycle management for their research data, according to international standards. The aim is to support FAIR by Design: from the first steps of producing FAIR data and Data Management Planning to the final steps of depositing data in public archives.”² The expansion described in this report adds specific and practical research data management knowledge for several Life Science domains. As the RDMkit is highly interlinked, this deliverable reports all extensions since the started toolkit (D3.1).

“The vision of the Toolkit has matured into three, interlinked, streams:

1. **The RDMkit**, a website-based guide for life scientists and data stewards in their efforts to better manage their research data.
2. **Tool Assemblies**, which are examples of combining tools to cover the distinct stages of the RDM Lifecycle and assembly patterns to report how tools can be combined and replaced by local specialisations.
3. **Data Stewardship Wizard**, which leads data stewards through decision trees to choose the right tools, resources and practices when preparing their data management plans.”³

The RDMkit has been the main focus in WP3 so far and was released for beta testing on the 31st of January and publicly the 31st of March 2021. It provides rapid and maximum benefit to Life Science communities linked with the involved ELIXIR Nodes and effectively coordinates and integrates the work of the CONVERGE WPs around a common goal. It is also a valuable resource for funders as is demonstrated by the HorizonEurope programme guide, released on the 26th of June 2021, explicitly recommending the RDMkit. The RDMkit has a broad target audience ranging from researchers, data managers and data stewards in laboratories, facilities or universities to project consortium coordinators, funding agencies and policy makers.

The RDMkit consists of static web pages, which are generated with Jekyll⁴ from easy to edit markdown files under version control in git in a GitHub repository (<https://github.com/elixir-europe/rdmkit>).

After the public release further content has been added through two virtual events (contentathons), organized by WP3 in May and June 2021, in which RDMkit editors and contributors from WP5 discussed and extended the RDMkit to better cover the needs of a set of domains including those of the demonstrator use cases. In addition to this, contributors representing different domains outside of ELIXIR CONVERGE have also started to add to the RDMkit by following the established

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4501634>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4501634>

⁴ <https://github.com/jekyll/jekyll>

contribution and editorial processes.

The demonstrator projects or use cases pertain to data management tools and best practices in several domains. The topics added by WP5 into RDMkit for this deliverable include: Epitranscriptomics, marine metagenomics, human genomics data, specifically in Norway and Luxembourg ELIXIR Nodes, and the EBI Covid-19 Data Portal. Importantly, communities outside WP5 volunteered to contribute to RDMkit content. For instance, the microbial biotechnology and the bioimaging communities happily contributed to RDMkit, acknowledging the key role of RDMkit in disseminating data management tools and best practices. Moreover, descriptions of local/national infrastructure have been included in RDMkit as inspiring examples of integrated tools and services, including national infrastructure solutions, for research data management in Life Sciences.

This deliverable reports on the extension of the RDMkit based on the first wave demonstrators (WP5) and additional content added since the public release. Extensions are documented through screenshot examples and we also describe observed challenges and further steps.

The RDMkit is available at <https://rdm.elixir-europe.org/> and <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/> (aliases) and is enabled by 90 contributors, describing 270 tools on 70 individual pages. The RDMkit has been visited by 2,900 individuals from 72 countries in the first two months since its official public release in May 2021.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	Yes
Key Result 1. 2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	Yes
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	No
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	No
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	No
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to	Yes

integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	Yes
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	Yes
Key Result 3.4: Enable 'FAIR at source' practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	Yes
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No
Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	Yes

3. Introduction

The RDMkit has been designed to guide life scientists in their efforts to better manage their research data following the FAIR Principles. It addresses the various steps of the data lifecycle and the considerations relevant for research data management linked with each life cycle stage. RDMkit can be navigated via a set of perspectives/views: 'data life cycle', 'role', 'domain', 'problem', 'tools and resources' and 'tool assembly'. The design, aim and intelinage of the RDMkit is described in ELIXIR-CONVERGE D3.1. Report on 'Assembled starter toolkit' ⁵.

3.1 Scope of Deliverable

The scope of this deliverable is to describe the approach and results of further extension of the RDMkit with a focus on content from the demonstrator use cases, beyond the state of the starter toolkit.

The knowledge gained from the demonstrator use cases is presented in the RDMkit in focused form in 'your domain' and 'tool assembly' pages.

1. **Your Domain Pages** addresses RDM Challenges specific to particular life science domains. Challenges specific to domains such as (meta)data types, organism species or areas are highlighted in these pages e.g. Human-Subject research, Marine Metagenomics. These pages list core considerations and solutions for each domain.
2. **Tool Assemblies** are examples of combining tools to cover the key functional areas (called "problems" in the RDMkit) to provide data management across several stages of the RDM Lifecycle. These can be tools that one or several ELIXIR Nodes or communities combine to support RDM that can be picked up or accessed and used by others. The assemblies can be focused for users in a specific location and/or for users within a specific domain.

The first wave of demonstrator projects describe the use of tools, standards and infrastructure for data management in the domains of Plant phenotype & genotype and marine metagenomics.

3.2 Relationship with other WPs

The RDMkit is a powerful and unifying focus area for WPs 1-5 and for the CONVERGE project as a whole. All these WPs have contributed to the design, content, oversight and extension of the RDMkit.

- WP1 Data Management experts contributed best practice and guidelines in 'your problem' pages.
- WP2 Training experts led work on defining persona and took charge of the role sections and will continue to deepen the connection between the RDMkit and TeSS, the ELIXIR Training Portal.
- WP4 assisted in outreach, the RDMkit communication planning and connections with EC and other policy makers.
- WP5: The achievement of this deliverable requires strong collaboration between WP3 and WP5 of the CONVERGE project. The collaboration between WP3 and WP5 was essential to identify the key data management aspects that are specific for each domain and use case. After that, we defined together the best way to add the content to RDMkit, according to its format and templates.

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4501634>

- WP7 is developing a major component of the RDMkit tool assemblies for sensitive human data and has been adding information on it to the RDMkit.
- WP8 has described the Covid-19 portal in a RDMkit tool assembly page.

3.3 Methodology for extension of the RDMkit

For extension of the RDMkit the same basic methodology as described in ELIXIR-CONVERGE D3.1. Report on ‘Assembled starter toolkit’⁶ was applied.

The Extension leveraged for this **incremental development** the agile principle of describing **user stories and observations** using the established **simple design and implementation** approach, while maintaining a **tightly scoped level** and **interlinking with existing other resources**.

The domain and assembly pages are tightly integrated with the other components of the RDMkit (Fig 1). Based on the first tool assembly in the starter toolkit (D3.1) on the Norwegian e-Infrastructure for Life Sciences (NeLS), we have created a minimal extendable and adaptable template for new tool assemblies. In future work we plan to refine and generalize this description template based on a wider selection of tool assemblies to show how tools can be combined in general.

Figure 1 diagram of interlinkage of the different RDMkit components through lists of links and cross referencing

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4501634>

The RDMKit was extended, gathering content from three different groups of contributors:

- Domain experts from the first & second wave demonstrators in ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP5 as described in D5.1⁷ and ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP8
- Experts on local/national infrastructures from the institutions participating in ELIXIR-CONVERGE
- Domain experts outside of ELIXIR and ELIXIR-CONVERGE; including experts from other ESFRIs such as Euro-BioImaging

The work has been performed through continuous contributions and through two designated contentathons, which were organized through online video conferencing platforms. In both cases the work described relies on the extension processes as described in milestone M3.3: Contributions are following the established RDMkit contribution guidelines and code of conduct, and are reviewed by the Editorial board with defined guidelines.

4. Description of work accomplished

Since the public release of the starter toolkit RDMkit (2021-02-01), 35 contributors have performed 498 file changes in 409 commits to the RDMkit github repository totaling in >135 new tools descriptions, 8 new tool assemblies and 4 new domain pages. The changes since the initial beta release can in detail be displayed through the version control system on github⁸. Fig 2 shows a continuous and steady level of contributions to the RDMkit.

Figure 2 Commits to the RDMkit repository in total (upper panel) and per day (lower panel) since the starter toolkit version in February 2021; visualization generated with <https://vesoft-inc.github.io/github-statistics/>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4674491>

⁸ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/rdmkit/compare/v1.0.0-beta..v1.1.0>

4.1 Contentathons

The WP organised the following events with identical scope to extend the toolkit:

- Contentathon May 2021: training/orientation to the toolkit, Tool assembly and domain page focused content contribution, improvements on navigation
- Contentathon June 2021: training/orientation to the toolkit, Tool assembly and domain page focused content contribution, improvements on navigation

Table 1: Hackathon and Contentathon statistics

Event	Attendance	WP Coverage	Node Coverage
Contentathon May 2021	Day 1: 12 Day 2: 11	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5	BE, CH, DE, ES, FI, FR, LU, NO
Contentathon June 2021	Day 1 : 28 Day 2 : 24	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5	BE, CH, DE, ES, FR, LU, NO, SE & external contributors

These contentathons are part of milestone M3.2.2 'Hackathons to assemble toolkit'⁹.

4.2 Orientation help for tool assembly contributors

In addition to the existing guidance for contribution in the RDMkit and in the form of webinar recordings and presentation material, we have started to work on a template for Tool Assemblies. This is initially based on a minimal markdown template¹⁰ and a figure template to connect the described tools in a diagram (Figure 3). Both were based on the first tool assembly in RDMkit (the Norwegian e-Infrastructure for Life Sciences - NeLS).

We are encouraging the contributors of tool assemblies to provide the following information:

- Short summary and stages of the Data Life covered
- Intended audience and accessibility
- Details on addressed DM problems ('your problems') in the Data Life Cycle Stages
- Available Training material (optional; optional links to TeSS)
- Tools included in Tool Assembly (optional links to bio.tools, FAIRsharing and TeSS)
- Related pages

⁹ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1GExCKEfUbnSHvMYhqnTxEie0cbyeTpZ1fQ2_WQAB0sA/edit#slide=id.g75cc253543_3_33

¹⁰ https://github.com/elixir-europe/rdmkit/blob/master/pages/tool_assembly/TEMPLATE_tool_assembly.md

Figure 3 Optional template diagram for visualization of interconnected tools addressing different problems at different Data Life Cycle Stages in a Tool Assembly

Our early experiences show that these templates seem to work well for tool assembly descriptions from a (local) infrastructural perspective. Application of the templates for tool assemblies from a domain oriented perspective or for situations with multiple alternatives for one step were perceived as limiting in some cases. In other cases (Translational Biomedicine, Marine Metagenomics) both approaches were combined in one assembly with local infrastructure and domain specific tools. For future work the templates will be further refined and/or we will supply different templates for these two different approaches to connect tools. Alternatively, the demonstrators will work on how to anchor their tool assembly either locally in specific node infrastructures and/or via example projects.

4.3 Extension of the toolkit based on demonstrator use-cases

Based on the methodology developed in D5.1¹¹, refinements of domain pages (e.g. Biomolecular Simulation and Epitranscriptome) and concrete tool assembly pages (e.g. Translational Biomedicine and Marine Metagenomics) have been developed in collaboration with the demonstrator groups linked with WP5 and the others have been completed or further edited after outreach to the corresponding communities (e.g. Human Health, Plant Science). A method has been set up to enrich the DS Wizard knowledge model and start to link the RDMkit and DS Wizard (D3.3) in relation to the demonstrator (D5.2¹²).

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4674491>

¹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5139903>

4.4 Extension of the toolkit to fill gaps

Based on the gap analysis we compiled a list of topics to be added to the RDMkit¹³ (see also Milestone M3.6). Based on the methodology developed from WP1 Best Practises (see D1.1¹⁴), WP1 has organized meetings for contributors to the RDMkit, recruited through the Data Management Expert network on specific topics. This format has enabled a continuous influx of high quality content from experts on specific topics, addressing the gaps identified earlier.

4.5 Link of the toolkit to presentation of information in DS Wizard

DS Wizard has, as of version 3.0¹⁵, the possibility of a “deep link”. This functionality was added based on an architectural design of the desired interplay between DS Wizard and RDMkit. Following a deep link, a user will be taken to an anonymous Data Stewardship Plan, opened to a specific part of the questionnaire tree. If the user wants to preserve their work exploring the question tree, it can be turned into a DS Wizard project on demand to create a DMP.

Addition of DS Wizard Deep Links to RDMkit pages can help RDMkit users to explore the considerations and options described in the pages through a decision tree model. First matches of pages to equivalent parts of the DS Wizard knowledge model have been identified, and are being readied for mutual connections. As of version 3.1 the DSW includes the possibility to provide suggestions to the users through “project templates” - open DMPs with pre-filled suggestions. This will enable users to directly base their Data Stewardship Plan on domain specific recommendations provided by the demonstrator use-cases (D5.2¹⁶), accessible through the RDMkit.

4.6 Workshops, Dissemination and External Engagement

Within CONVERGE

- Meeting with DSW on integration of RDMkit and DSW, 24 June 2021

ELIXIR-wide

- ELIXIR AH 2021 Data Management Workshop¹⁷, 04 June 2021
- The FAIRcookbook community on integration of both resources, 01 July 2021
- ELIXIR AH 2021 Plant Science community workshop, 01 June 2021
- ELIXIR Webinar, Towards professionalising data stewardship, 18 May 2021¹⁸
- ELIXIR Mid Term Review, in Interoperability Platform presentation, 8th June 2021

¹³ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/rdmkit/issues/427>

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4501945>

¹⁵ <https://docs.ds-wizard.org/en/latest/dev/roadmap.html>

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5139903>

¹⁷ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/181At1EEuhdvgGX8Ldgd2K0Mx7xWUz5ePvuOL2hsFehg/edit#heading=h.2zr11fem1ipw>

¹⁸ <https://elixir-europe.org/events/elixir-webinar-towards-professionalising-data-stewardship>

External (dissemination)

International Presentations / Panels

ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP3 open webinar “Research Data Management Kit (RDMkit)”, online 01 March 2021.	Focus
Invited presentation, "FAIR workshop for European Commission Project and Policy Officers", 29 April 2021.	Focus
International data management policies and practices: A life science perspective, online - Canada, 01 June 2021.	Focus
"FAIR characterization data on genetic resources: making it real?", online COST Action CA17111, 01 July 2021.	Focus
Invited webinar NSF Convergence Accelerator Series Tracks A&B webinar, 19th May 2021 ¹⁹ , (Goble).	Featured
Invited presentation, National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine, workshop "Changing the Culture of Data Management and Sharing", 28 April 2021 (Goble) (online). RDMkit included in the “Blue Book” materials distributed to participants. Over 1600 participants.	Featured
Invited panelist, ESFRI clusters at RDA House of Commons, debate 1 ““Metadata. Everyone thinks it's a great idea, but no-one wants to use someone else's”, 19 April 2021 (Goble).	Featured
CA17111 Integrate COST action Annual Conference (virtual), 01 July 2021. 317 registered attendees from 37 countries (all continents represented), Academic and Industry	Highlighted
ISMB/ECCB virtual conference, NIH-ODSS session on FAIR Data Repositories, July 27 th 2021 (Goble).	Featured
Jisc and CNI Leaders Conference ²⁰ , Panel “Providing data science support to the research enterprise” 2021 July 8th 2021.	Highlighted

¹⁹ <http://spatial.ucsb.edu/2021/Carole-Goble>

²⁰ <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/cni-conference>

National

ELIXIR-UK Health Data Workshop, 21 June 2021 (Goble).	Featured
Dutch national Bioinformatics and systems biology conference BioSB2021. ²¹	Featured
RDA-NO Workshop Research Data Management in practice - Documentation and metadata, 31 May 2021 ²²	Highlighted

Meetings

RDMkit disseminated to:

- G7 Open Science WG, 7 May 2021 (Goble)
- Finnish Data Support Network, a collaboration network for data management support personnel in research organizations, 7 May 2021
- UKRI-BBSRC, MRC and NERC National Funding Councils in the UK
- Wellcome Trust

Training events

- ELIXIR-FI introduction to RDMkit in “BioMonth”, CSC supercomputing and data management training for bioscientists, 23 March 2021
- ELIXIR-NO introduction to RDMkit in 2 DMP workshops, 21 April and 16 June 2021²³
- ELIXIR-UK, RDMkit incorporated into the workplan of the UK’s DaSH programme for national RDM training fellowships²⁴.

Newsletters and mailing lists

- de.NBI quarterly newsletter
- EOSC-Life newsletter
- ELIXIR Newsletter
- RDA Norway mailing list
- National ELIXIR Node homepages

²¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4963900>

²² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/rda-norway/event/no-rda-workshop-research-data-management-practice-documentation-and-metadata>

²³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3693710>

²⁴ <https://elixiruknode.org/fair-data-stewardship-training-project/>

5. Results

Based on the established infrastructure and contribution processes, the RDMkit has further extended its content and now includes additional valuable information on considerations and solutions for problems in specific sub-domains of Life Science.

The RDMkit link: <https://rdm.elixir-europe.org/> and <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

The RDMkit Github link: <https://github.com/elixir-europe/rdmkit> a archived version of the release connected to the status of the RDMkit in this report can be found on zenodo²⁵.

5.1 Toolkit extensions from first and second wave demonstrator use-cases

Two months after the public release of the RDMkit, and six months after the beta release, out of the two first wave and four second wave demonstrator use cases, all except one second wave demonstrator use case have already identified relevant content and added it to the RDMkit. This information is provided to the users on ‘your domain’ and ‘tool assembly’ pages.

The content added through the demonstrator use cases is described in D5.2²⁶ in detail and is listed here in addition for the reader's convenience.

5.1.1 ‘Plant sciences’ domain page and ‘Plant phenotyping’ and ‘Plant genotyping’ tool assemblies (first wave demonstrator use-case #1)

Plant sciences ✎ edit

- Introduction
- Plant phenotyping metadata management
- Plant phenotyping data sharing and deposition
- Integrating plant phenotypic and molecular data
- Relevant tools and resources
- Training materials on plant data management

Introduction

The plant science domain includes studying the adaptation of plants to their environment, with applications ranging from improving crop yield or resistance to environmental conditions, to managing forest ecosystems.

Data integration and reuse are facilitators for understanding the play between genotype and environment to produce a phenotype, which requires integrating phenotyping experiments and genomic assays made on the same plant material, with geo-climatic data. Moreover, cross-species comparisons are often necessary to understand the mechanisms behind phenotypic traits, especially at the genotypic level, due to the gap in genomic knowledge between well-studied plant species (namely *Arabidopsis*) and newly sequenced ones.

The challenges to data integration stem from the multiple levels of heterogeneity in this domain, it encompasses a variety of species, ranging from model organisms, to crop species, to wild plants such as forest trees. These often need to be detailed at infra-specific levels (e.g. subspecies, varieties, but naming at these levels sometimes lacks consensus). Studies can take place in a diversity of settings including indoor (e.g. growth chamber, greenhouse) and outdoor settings (e.g. cultivated field, forest) which differ fundamentally on the requirements and manner of characterizing the environment. Phenotypic data can be collected manually or automatically (by sensors and drones), and be very diverse in nature, spanning physical measurements, the results of biochemical assays, and images. Some omics data can be considered as well as molecular phenotypes (e.g. transcriptome, metabolomes, ...). Thus the extension and depth of metadata required to describe a plant experiment in a FAIR-compliant way is very demanding for researchers.

Another particularity of this domain is the absence of central deposition databases for certain important data types, in particular data deriving from plant phenotyping experiments. Whereas datasets from plant omics experiments are typically deposited in global deposition databases for that type of experiment, those from phenotyping experiments remain in institutional or at best national repositories. This makes it difficult to find, access and interconnect plant phenotyping data.

Plant phenotyping metadata management

Description

It is recommended that metadata collection is contemplated from the start of the experiment and that the working environment facilitates metadata collection, storage, and validation throughout the project.

Figure 4 Plant sciences domain page

The plant sciences domain page²⁷ has been developed as part of the starter toolkit. Plant science is a wide domain with multiple levels of heterogeneity. Thus the extension and depth of metadata required to describe a plant experiment in a FAIR-compliant way and the absence of central deposition databases for e.g. plant phenotyping experiments are very demanding for researchers. The plant sciences domain page gives guidance on handling of phenotypic data and its integration with molecular data and points to relevant tools, tools assemblies and standards.

²⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5110061>

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5139903>

²⁷ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/plant_sciences.html

Figure 5 Plant phenotyping tool assembly page and diagram

The plant genomics tool assembly page²⁸ describes tools for the management of plant genomics and genotyping data throughout its lifecycle, with a particular focus on ensuring traceability of the biological materials to enable interoperability with plant phenotyping data.

5.1.2 ‘Marine metagenomics’ domain page and ‘Marine Metagenomics’ tool assembly (first wave demonstrator use-case #3)

Figure 6 Marine metagenomics domain page

The marine metagenomics domain page²⁹ has been developed as part of the starter toolkit. Marine metagenomics is characterized by large datasets that require access to substantial storage and High-Performance Computing (HPC) for running complex and memory-intensive analysis pipelines, and therefore are difficult to handle for typical end-users and beyond the resources of many service providers. The marine metagenomics domain page gives guidance on these topics and points users to relevant tools, tool assemblies and standards.

²⁸ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/plant_genomics_assembly.html

²⁹ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/marine_metagenomics.html

Figure 7 Marine metagenomics tool assembly page and diagram

The marine metagenomics tool assembly³⁰, developed by students and researchers in Norway, contains resources and software tools for both data management (Planning, Processing, Storing and Sharing), data analysis and training. It is built on the Norwegian e-Infrastructure for Life Sciences (NeLS) tool assembly of ELIXIR Norway and the Marine Metagenomics Platform (MMP).

5.1.3 ‘Human data’ domain page and ‘Translational Biomedicine’ tool assembly (second wave demonstrator use-case #4)

Figure 8 Marine metagenomics tool assembly page and diagram

Human Data domain page³¹ has been developed as part of the starter toolkit. Research with human data poses additional requirements for the entire data lifecycle. Data management planning needs to take into account the ethics and legal requirements. Data collection, handling, sharing and

³⁰ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/marine_metagenomics_assembly.html

³¹ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/human_data.html

re-use needs to occur under respective safeguards. The Human Data domain page gives guidance on these topics with pointers to relevant tools, tools assemblies and standards.

TransMed Assembly ELIXIR

Data management tool assembly by ELIXIR Luxembourg supporting projects in Translational Biomedicine. The TransMed assembly is available as a hosted service from ELIXIR Luxembourg, it also acts as an RDM blueprint for the wider research community.

- What is the TransMed data and computing tool assembly?
- Who can use the TransMed data and computing tool assembly?
- For what purpose can the TransMed assembly be used?
- What tools are used within the TransMed assembly?

What is the TransMed data and computing tool assembly?

The TransMed data and computing tool assembly is an infrastructure provided by ELIXIR Luxembourg for clinical and translational projects. TransMed assembly provides the tools for managing ongoing projects that often require the management of cohort recruitment, and processing of samples, data and metadata. This entails GDPR-compliant and secure data collection, storage, curation, standardisation integration and analysis of clinical data and associated molecular, imaging and sensor/mobile data and metadata.

TransMed tool assembly is also a blueprint showing how a collection of tools can be combined to support data lifecycle management in clinical and translational projects.

Who can use the TransMed data and computing tool assembly?

All researchers can use tools in the TransMed assembly individually or in combination depending on their project needs. Most of the tools in the TransMed assembly are open-source and can be re-used. ELIXIR Luxembourg provides know-how transfer and training on the tool assembly upon request from researchers and data steward organisations. To make a request please contact info@elixir-luxembourg.org.

Additionally, ELIXIR Luxembourg provides hosting of the TransMed assembly. Hosting of tools and data is free of charge for national users. For international users hosting of data (up to 10TB) is free on the basis that the data is shared with the wider research community with an appropriate access model such as controlled access. For international users, charges for the hosting tools and hosting of large datasets are evaluated on a case-by-case, please contact info@elixir-luxembourg.org for details.

For what purpose can the TransMed assembly be used?

Figure 9 TransMed tool assembly page and diagram

The TransMed data and computing tool assembly³² is an infrastructure provided by ELIXIR Luxembourg for clinical and translational projects. The TransMed assembly provides the tools for managing ongoing projects that often require the management of cohort recruitment, and processing of samples, data and metadata. This entails GDPR-compliant and secure data collection, storage, curation, standardisation integration and analysis of clinical data and associated molecular, imaging and sensor/mobile data and metadata.

TransMed tool assembly is also a blueprint showing how a collection of tools can be combined to support data lifecycle management in clinical and translational projects.

In addition to the TransMed tool assembly, the TSD and the CSC tool assembly, provided for users in Norway and Finland respectively, also include local resources for secure data management of sensitive data. Both are also accessible through the EOSC service catalogue to European users.

³² https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/transmed_assembly.html

5.1.4 ‘Biomolecular simulation data’ domain page (second wave demonstrator use-case #6)

Figure 10 Biomolecular simulation data domain page

The Biomolecular domain page³³ has been developed as part of the starter toolkit. The field of biomolecular simulation only relatively recently started to store and share (bio)simulation data to be reused for new, unexpected projects, and started discussions about making their biomolecular simulation data more FAIR. In this page, challenges specific to the biomolecular simulation domain are highlighted together with several current possibilities moving towards the direction of FAIRification of this type of data.

5.1.5 ‘Epitranscriptome data’ domain page (second wave demonstrator use-case #2)

Figure 11 Epitranscriptome data domain page

In the epitranscriptome domain page³⁴ characteristic challenges are mentioned together with the main considerations and solutions that can be used as a solution for epitranscriptome data management. The detection of RNA modifications requires ad hoc bioinformatics pipelines as well as the use of computing intensive tools to handle the huge amount of available deep transcriptome sequencing experiments. A fruitful organization of data and computational workflows is therefore important for a FAIRification of the epitranscriptome data domain.

³³ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/biomolecular_simulation_data.html

³⁴ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/epitranscriptome_data.html

5.2 Toolkit extensions regarding local/national infrastructure

5.2.1 'CSC - Finland' tool assembly

CSC - Finland ✓ last time

This is a Data Management tool assembly from CSC - IT Center for Science and ELIXIR Finland that provides high-quality ICT expert services for researchers in Finland and their collaborators.

- What is the CSC data management tool assembly?
- Who can use the CSC data management tool assembly?
- How can you access the CSC data management tool assembly?
- For what can you use the CSC data management tool assembly?
- Where can you find training materials and events about the CSC data management tool assembly?
- What tools are used within the CSC data management tool assembly?

What is the CSC data management tool assembly?

CSC - IT Center for Science and ELIXIR Finland provides services, tools and software for managing research data throughout the project life cycle. Services cover computing environments, analysis programs, tools for storing and sharing data during the project as well as opening and discovering research data. Furthermore, ELIXIR-FI provides flexible infrastructure for bioinformatics data analysis. Services are actively developed, and hence, please visit CSC web pages for the latest updates.

Who can use the CSC data management tool assembly?

CSC and ELIXIR-FI services are accessible for researchers in Finland and to foreign collaborators of Finland-based research groups. Most of CSC's services are free-of-charge for academic research, education and training purposes in Finnish higher education institutions and in state research institutes. Researchers can start using services by registering an account and get bioinformatics user support from our service desk.

How can you access the CSC data management tool assembly?

You can access all CSC services through several secure authentication methods. Start by registering an account at CSC with your home organization HAA or VIRTU login or by contacting our service desk. Afterwards you can also use ELIXIR login. Find more information from CSC accounts and support web pages how to get access to different services.

Figure 12 CSC tool assembly page and diagram

The data management tool assembly³⁵ from CSC - IT Center for Science and ELIXIR Finland describes national services accessible for researchers in Finland and for collaborators of Finland-based research groups. CSC provides high-quality ICT expert services for research data management throughout the project life cycle and ELIXIR-FI provides flexible infrastructure for bioinformatics data analysis. The tool assembly is complemented with a selection of services for management of sensitive data, which are also accessible through the EOSC-Hub service catalogue³⁶.

5.2.2 'TSD - Norway' tool assembly

TSD for sensitive data - Norway ✓ last time

This is a Data Management tool assembly for sensitive data around TSD. TSD as an infrastructure is aimed for researchers in Norway and their collaborators, but can be used by anyone.

- What is the Norwegian tools assembly for sensitive data - TSD data management tools assembly?
- Who can use the TSD data management tools assembly?
- What can you use the TSD data management tools assembly for?
- Where can I find training materials, documentations and events about the TSD data management tool assembly?
- What tools are used within the TSD data management tools assembly?

What is the Norwegian tools assembly for sensitive data - TSD data management tools assembly?

The Norwegian ELIXIR tools assembly for sensitive data is centred around TSD - literally for: services for sensitive data (<https://www.usc.no/eng/ish/services/research-sensitive-data/>) is an infrastructure provided by the University of Oslo (UO). Together with the other complementary tools provided by ELIXIR, TSD can be used for the management of sensitive data, including handling of human data. This assembly covers Planning, Processing, Archiving and Sharing Data by the design and offer Data Storage capacities and tools for transfer of sensitive data, following the requirements of the EU general data protection regulations (GDPR) and its Norwegian implementation.

Who can use the TSD data management tools assembly?

Resources on TSD itself are accessible for international users through EOSC and directly through the University of Oslo. Researchers in Norway can in addition obtain access through the national e-infrastructure program Sigma2 and additional storage quotas (up to 10TB) for existing TSD projects through the Norwegian bioinformatics support desk contact@bioinformatics.no. If you are affiliated to a Norwegian institution which has already stipulated a data processing and/or service agreement with TSD this document can be used or amended to account for your project. Otherwise, you can establish a data agreement for your individual project by contacting tso-consortium@usc.no.

Figure 13 TSD tool assembly page and diagram

The tool assembly around the Norwegian service for sensitive data (TSD)³⁷ describes how tools within the TSD environment can be used together with ELIXIR tools to manage sensitive personal

³⁵ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/fi_csc_assembly.html

³⁶ <https://eosc-hub.eu/services/Services%20for%20sensitive%20data>

³⁷ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/NO_TSD_assembly.html

data in a secure manner. TSD is accessible for users within Norway and to external users through the EOSC-Hub service catalogue and the EOSC marketplace³⁸.

5.2.3 'IFB France' tool assembly

Figure 14 TSD tool assembly page and diagram

The IFB tool assembly³⁹ describes how the different services offered by IFB (Institut Français de Bioinformatique) and its partners can be used to achieve better data management practices. The services can be used by french scientists and their European partners.

³⁸ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/tds>

³⁹ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/fr_ifb_assembly.html

5.3 Other toolkit extensions

5.3.1 Covid-19 Data Portal from WP8

COVID-19 Data Portal edit me

The COVID-19 Data Portal brings together relevant datasets for sharing and analysis in an effort to accelerate coronavirus research. It enables researchers to upload, access and analyse COVID-19 related reference data and specialist datasets.

- What is the European COVID-19 Data Portal?
- How the portal is useful for researchers and how it is supposed to fit into their processes?
- What are the components for the COVID-19 Data Portal?
- What country specific instances are there and how new instances are deployed?

What is the European COVID-19 Data Portal?

The European COVID-19 Data Platform was launched to facilitate the urgent need to share and analyse COVID-19 data and thus accelerate research that will provide responses and build solutions, such as vaccines, treatments and public health interventions. The Platform comprises three core components, the SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs, the Federated European Genome phenome archive and the COVID-19 Data Portal. The COVID-19 Data Portal brings together and continuously updates relevant COVID-19 datasets from a breadth of analytical platforms. Data are submitted using the SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs functions or via other major centres of biomedical data. The data available from the COVID-19 Data Portal cover raw and assembled viral and human sequences, protein structures, proteomics, gene and protein expression data, compound screening, metabolomics and imaging data. COVID-19 relevant literature publications and pre-prints are also integrated. The aim is to have a wide variety of open data from across the globe systematised and easily accessible to researchers following FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). The European COVID-19 Data Platform enables national data producers to share biobiomolecular data with the international scientific community, making these data available for reuse. Ultimately it aims to allow for rapid analysis and dissemination to inform research, public health and health communities and in an evidence-based manner.

How the portal is useful for researchers and how it is supposed to fit into their processes?

Researchers benefit the COVID-19 Data Portal in a host of ways:

- Discoverability of COVID-19 relevant biomolecular data and related literature
- Support for the management, sharing, analysis and publication of newly-generated data
- Access to integrated COVID-19 data across multiple assay platforms
- Reusable data
- Flexible access via web, API and FTP interfaces
- Access to data exploration and analysis tools

What are the components for the COVID-19 Data Portal?

The COVID-19 Data Portal data flow schematic, showing collation, indexing, integration and user access functions.

The following reusable components will be of value to data stewards:

- **Discovery API** with documented COVID-19 index points across data and literature resources covered by the COVID-19 Data Portal.
- **Options for membership** of the network of national COVID-19 Data Portals, currently comprising some 8 partners.
- **Toolkit** providing elements to support nation COVID-19 Data Portal construction.
- **Open source** web application to establish national COVID-19 Data Portal, courtesy of ELIXIR Sweden.
- **Support** via ecovid19@ebi.ac.uk

Figure 15 Covid-19 Data Portal tool assembly page and illustration

The COVID-19 Data Portal brings together relevant datasets for sharing and analysis in an effort to accelerate coronavirus research. It enables researchers to upload, access and analyse COVID-19 related reference data and specialist datasets. The tool assembly page⁴⁰ was added to the RDMkit though WP7 and WP8.

5.3.2 XNAT-PIC

XNAT-PIC edit me

XNAT for Preclinical Imaging Centers (XNAT-PIC) is a set of tools to store, process and share preclinical imaging studies built on top of the XNAT imaging informatics platform.

- Summary
- What is XNAT-PIC?
- Who is XNAT-PIC intended for?
- Which task can be solved with XNAT-PIC?
- Where can you find training materials and events about XNAT-PIC?
- Citation
- Tools used within XNAT-PIC?

Summary

Preclinical imaging centers deal with many challenges mostly related to the variety of imaging instrumentation yielding huge volumes of raw data. The current procedures to collect, share and reuse preclinical image data are inefficient, thus creating an urgent need of standardization in terms of data storage and image processing. **XNAT for Preclinical Imaging Centers (XNAT-PIC)** has been developed to overcome this limitation by extending XNAT's basic functionalities to meet the needs of preclinical imaging facilities.

What is XNAT-PIC?

XNAT for Preclinical Imaging Centers (XNAT-PIC) consists of a set of tools built in python and MATLAB to store, process and share preclinical imaging studies built on top of the XNAT imaging informatics platform.

Who is XNAT-PIC intended for?

XNAT-PIC is intended for scientists, researchers and data stewards working in the preclinical and biomedical imaging field to support image data management and processing.

Which task can be solved with XNAT-PIC?

XNAT-PIC is a set of tools to support preclinical imaging scientists in their data management and processing needs. The Extensible Neuroimaging Archive Toolkit (XNAT) is an imaging informatics platform developed by the Neuroinformatics Research Group of the Washington University for the management, storage and analysis of biomedical image data. XNAT is an open source project that can support a wide range of imaging modalities thanks to its extensibility.

XNAT-PIC consists of:

1. **MRDICOM processor** (Magnetic Resonance) images and convert them from Paravision® (Bruker, Inc., Ettlingen, MA) file format to DICOM standard
2. **XNAT-PIC Uploader** to import and store multimodal DICOM image datasets to XNAT
3. **XNAT-PIC Pipelines** for analyzing single- or multiple subjects within the same project in XNAT.

Figure 16 XNAT-PIC

This tool assembly⁴¹ describes XNAT for Preclinical Imaging Centers (XNAT-PIC), a set of tools to store, process and share preclinical imaging studies built on top of the XNAT imaging informatics

⁴⁰ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/covid19_data_portal.html

⁴¹ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/xnat_pic_tool_assembly.html

platform. XNAT-PIC has been developed and added to the RDMkit by Euro-Biolmaging. It is one of the demonstrator within EOSC-Life⁴².

5.3.3 Additional 'your problem' pages

- Compliance monitoring⁴³
- Existing data⁴⁴ (RDM Focus group, organized through WP1, with external contributions)
- Identifiers⁴⁵ (RDM Focus group, organized through WP1, with external contributions)
- Documentation and metadata⁴⁶ (RDM Focus group, organized through WP1, with external contributions)

6. Conclusions

Six months after the beta release and two months after the public release, the RDMkit is still an evolving resource, but has reached a phase of linear growth and steady contribution. Even though the RDMkit has only recently been released, several relevant communities have already started using it and it has also become part of the recommendations of several institutions and funders.

Thanks to clear and efficient contribution and editorial processes and its lean design the status of the RDMkit is ahead of the scheduled progress and includes **Domain pages** and **Tool Assemblies** from more than just the first wave demonstrator use cases from WP5. Soon the RDMkit will fully cover all the described use cases in WP5.

Additional value for the end-users will be added by interlinking the **Data Stewardship Wizard** with the RDMkit, this will enable the end-users to receive guidance through decision trees and relevant domain specific DMP guidance provided by the work performed in WP5 on DMP processes.

In addition, the RDMkit contribution process has already proved to enable efficient uptake of knowledge from Life Science domains and their tool assemblies outside of ELIXIR and we are well positioned to further scale this activity in conjunction with the continued dissemination through WP4.

The maintenance and consolidation of the existing content is enabled through a very engaged Editorial Board, an activity which has to continue throughout and beyond the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project period to safe-guard the RDMkit as a sustainable resource.

⁴² <https://www.eosc-life.eu/d5/>

⁴³ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/compliance_monitoring.html

⁴⁴ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/existing_data.html

⁴⁵ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/identifiers.html>

⁴⁶ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/metadata_management.html

7. Impact

The RDMkit is enabled by the highly interconnected and efficient work of ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP1-5 across all ELIXIR Nodes.

After its public release the RDMkit has been received positively in both the Life Science and general research data management community on the general guidance on research data management, as well as the Life Science specific guidance.

The RDMkit is recommended by European funders:

- in the Horizon Europe Program Guide as the "resource for Data Management guidelines and good practices for the Life Sciences."⁴⁷
- in presentations from the Research Council of Norway

Multiple research institutions recommend the RDMkit for their users, including:

- Norwegian University for Life Sciences⁴⁸
- University of Bergen⁴⁹

8. Next Steps

Based on the review of the RDMkit, reported in Milestone M3.6 (toolkit review and gap analysis based demonstrator support) the description in the domain pages, derived from the WP5 demonstrator use cases, will be further refined and completed. The Editorial Board will continue to meet bi-weekly. The RDMkit will continually evolve as a living site throughout the CONVERGE project duration and beyond. This is a long-term commitment.

The next steps follow several intertwined lines of work:

Content

- All WP5 demonstrator use cases will be presented in the RDMkit with domain pages and practical tool assemblies (D3.5). Together with WP5 we will also review and consolidate the currently existing domain-specific content.
- We will ensure full Bioschema markup compliance for the RDMkit

Integration

- WP2 has started a process to extend the EDAM ontology with data management terminology to allow semantic descriptions of training material in TeSS, this will further also benefit the RDMkit on the linked training material but also as tools in bio.tools can then be semantically described in more detail and linked more efficiently to the RDMkit. WP2 is currently preparing 2 events to curate existing and add additional training material to the RDMkit.

⁴⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

⁴⁸ <https://www.nmbu.no/forskning/forskere/forskningsdata/node/42936>

⁴⁹ <https://www.uib.no/en/ub/111372/open-access-research-data#subject-specific-support>

- The DSW development team has recently developed the possibility for deep links to single questions in DSW⁵⁰. We will use this possibility to cross-link and integrate both resources in depth (Task 3.3 and D3.3) and will further link the demonstrator use case-oriented DMP processes (see D5.2⁵¹) in the near future also by making use of the “project template” feature to provide domain specific recommendations to the users.
- We plan to integrate and crosslink the RDMkit with additional resources, including:
 - FAIRPlus FAIR Cookbook
 - Incorporation of results of the **Data Submissions Brokering** explorations (Task 1.2)
 - EOSC Portal Catalogue & Marketplace
 - Further calls to capture more tools and get tools registered in bio.tools
- We will explore and implement possibilities to track the relationship between tools and their locally deployed instances, e.g. on a national level at the **BioHackathon 2021** (project #6)⁵²

Community Contribution

- We will continue to reach out to other infrastructures and communities, including other ESFRI infrastructures, national and European projects on FAIR data management and local initiatives, and invite them to contribute to the RDMkit with their domain specific knowledge in form of **tool assemblies** and **domain pages** e.g. at events like the BioHackathon 2021 (project #6).
- We will continue the efficient and focused activity to improve your **problem** pages with contributors recruited through the WP1 best practise group and the data management expert network.

ELIXIR Platform Embedding

We see the RDMkit fulfilling a powerful role as an unifying portal for life scientists and data stewards onto the FAIR activities of ELIXIR, and as a fully embedded flagship resource unifying activities across ELIXIR (Fig 17). We have already seen engagement with the ELIXIR Communities and Focus groups, where, as with the CONVERGE WPs, the RDMkit has proved a powerful convergence mechanism and a showcase for outcomes. Similar observations were made with ELIXIR projects like FAIRplus and the integration of the FAIR Cookbook. We aim to incorporate the RDMkit into the roadmaps and activities of all ELIXIR programmes, implementation studies and most importantly of all, the Platforms - in particular Tools, Data and interoperability.

⁵⁰ <https://docs.ds-wizard.org/en/v3.1.0/dev/roadmap.html#id3>

⁵¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5139903>

⁵² <https://biohackathon-europe.org/projects.html>

Figure 17 The RDMkit framed as an integrating portal onto ELIXIR's FAIR services and activities

9. Deviation from Description of Action

The proposal envisaged the Tool Assemblies and a portal to the assemblies; the RDMkit was realised as the toolkit that was actually needed to link up the WPs and tasks, build community and exchange knowledge.

The order of the WP5 first and second wave demonstrators has been adjusted earlier in comparison to the original proposal (see D5.1). The extension of the toolkit with content from the WP5 demonstrator use cases has started early and content from the demonstrators has already been part of the starter toolkit. All demonstrator use cases except #5 (FAIR encoding and access to Toxicology data) are part of the RDMkit at the current stage with extensions from both the first wave and second wave demonstrators.

10. Appendix

10.1 Editorial Board

Bert Droesbeke (BE), Carole Goble (UK), Daniel Faria (PT), Flora D'Anna (BE), Frederik Coppens (BE), Mijke Jetten (NL), Munazah Andrabi (UK), Niclas Jareborg (SE), Pinar Alper (LU), Rob Hooft (NL), Ulrike Wittig (DE), Laura Portell Silva (ES), Martin Cook (ELIXIR Hub), Korbinian Bösl (NO)

(https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/editorial_board.html)